

DISPERSIBLE TABLETS — PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW DOSAGE FORM: CASE STUDY OF NYSTATIN DISPERSIBLE TABLET FORMULATION

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Relevance: Dispersible tablets are one of the most promising solid dosage forms, offering ease of use, especially for patients with swallowing difficulties such as children, the elderly, and patients with dysphagia. The ability to obtain a suspension from a tablet immediately before administration makes this form attractive for expanding the range of oral drugs, including antifungal agents like nystatin.

Objective of the Study: To develop and optimize the formulation of nystatin dispersible tablets suitable for use as a suspension in patients who have difficulty taking solid oral forms.

Materials and Methods: Active substance: Nystatin **Initial formulations:** 10 variants with different types of disintegrants and fillers, as well as other excipients, including flavoring agents and sweeteners. **Excipients used:** Croscarmellose sodium, sodium starch glycolate, povidone, sorbitol, mannitol, microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), starch, lactose, xanthan gum, and their combinations.

Parameters evaluated: Appearance, weight, hardness, disintegration time.

Equipment: ERWEKA ZT 320 Tablet and Capsule Disintegration Tester; ERWEKA TAR 220 Friability Tester; PTK PR-LM Tablet Press FRITSCH laboratory sieves with sizes: 0.4 mm; 0.6 mm; 0.8 mm

Results: Initially, the impact of various disintegrants was studied; however, achieving the regulatory disintegration time (within 3 minutes) was not successful. After shifting focus to the selection and combination of fillers, satisfactory disintegration results were still not achieved. None of the tested formulations provided stable disintegration within the required time frame. Variants with croscarmellose sodium and sodium starch glycolate demonstrated acceptable disintegration times but produced tablets that were too fragile. The addition of povidone improved mechanical strength but negatively affected dispersibility. Formulations containing starch and sodium carboxymethyl starch showed uneven disintegration and a tendency to form gels. Variants with microcrystalline cellulose had satisfactory mechanical properties but poor dispersibility. In all cases, high sensitivity of the composition to humidity was observed, which complicated the tableting process.

Conclusion: The development of an effective dispersible dosage form of nystatin proved to be more challenging than initially anticipated. The study showed that the choice of fillers and their combinations significantly influences tablet disintegration, and none of the tested formulations met the required standards. Further research is needed to identify suitable functional excipients, possibly involving modern super-disintegrants and particle surface modification technologies.